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VISUAL ANTHROPOLOGY AND PUBLIC DESIGN

CAN THE ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THESE FIELDS GENERATE VALUABLE INSIGHTS INTO THE DIVERSE PATTERNS OF URBAN BEHAVIOUR?

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ABSTRACT

Understanding the users' needs in public spaces is often a challenge to industrial designers. Cities are growing fast and urban spaces should be adapted to these changes. This paper probes the utilization of visual anthropology theories and methods as tools to support the interpretation of the city dwellers' diverse behaviours. Adaptations and interventions performed by the public are regarded as hints of their desires, which should be fulfilled by the urban elements, that is, the products that are placed in urban spaces. In order to verify such assumptions, a cultural inventory was conducted in selected public spaces in Ottawa, Canada. The researcher looked for material evidences of modifications to urban products made by the population and documented them in photographs. The images provided the study with useful data, whose analysis provided possible insights into public design development.

Keywords: visual anthropology, public design, public spaces.

INTRODUCTION

Public spaces are becoming progressively more important as the world population increases. People put more expectation on the quality of public environments and facilities, which are capable of determining the quality of the everyday urban life (Siu, 2009). At present, these spaces should fulfil not only city users' functional needs but also their social, cultural, psychological and ideological demands (Siu, 2009).

The study of anthropological subjects becomes central in this discussion. In order to understand the

needs, habits, values and beliefs of individuals or groups of users, design researchers have become more and more interested in cultural studies (Siu, 2005) and design culture (Julier, 2006). This paper intends to probe the association of visual anthropology principles with current public design issues. Possessing substantial training in visual skills, design researchers are highly qualified for analyzing images. Anthropologists, on the other hand, might offer a new perspective on how people relate to objects such as the urban elements that are available in public spaces.

The research explores the concept of visual anthropology and its implications to design research. Making use of photography, visual anthropologists are capable of obtaining accurate visual information, which enables them to, for instance, carry out cultural inventories. Photographs capture not only material objects but also the relationship between artefacts and their arrangement. In the urban context, pictures can support a more detailed analysis of the wide range of symbols that are manifested in the streets, plazas, and public spaces in general. They capture both the products and solutions that are offered to users as well as the public's response to them. Designers and design researchers may contribute in a different way to the analysis of this graphic material.

As an attempt to explore the application of visual anthropological methods to the public design field, a photographic cultural inventory was conducted in public spaces in Ottawa. The intention was to identify material evidences that could characterize the relationship between city dwellers and public design elements. Rather than just glancing at urban areas, the researcher attempted to gaze (Shields,

2003) or, in other words, look attentively and carefully at diverse instances of user adaptations to objects and interventions in spaces for further data for analysis. The findings suggest some cultural and social aspects that should be considered in the development of urban elements and spaces.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

VISUAL ANTHROPOLOGY

It is through perception, largely visual and auditory, that we respond to the humanness that surrounds us (Collier & Collier, 1986). Visual anthropology inquires into “all that humans make for others to see” (Ruby, 2000). In this sense, facial expressions, costumes, symbolic uses of space, abodes and living spaces as well as pictorial artefacts such as rock engravings and holographs become objects of investigation. Visual anthropologists believe that culture is not only manifested in abstract ways, but it is also expressed through “visible symbols embedded in gestures, ceremonies, rituals, and artefacts situated in constructed and natural environments” (Ruby, 2000). The socio-cultural self may be therefore understood as the combination of the scenarios in which one participates as a performer or an audience member (Ruby, 2000: 241).

The term visual anthropology is commonly associated with films produced by Robert Flaherty, Robert Gardner, Tim Asch and others whose subject is the cultural other or native peoples:

When the phrase anthropology and film is heard, many people think of the so-called ethnographic films about exotic peoples(...) Nanook of the North , The Hunters, Dead Birds, The Ax Fight, and The Feast come to mind. These foundational works have represented the essence of genre for several generations (Ruby, 2000).

Nonetheless, still photographs have also been used as tools to examine cultural contexts. The eye of the camera provides researchers with accurate visual information, a considerable advantage for the modern researcher who is, in general, a poor observer (Collier & Collier, 1986). It is important to reinforce, however, that the camera has no selective process; “it is just only a means to an end: holistic and accurate observation” (Collier & Collier, 1986). Only the researcher can guide the camera’s focus to capture meaningful information for the study. As

stated by Collier & Collier (1986) “the camera is another instrumental extension of our senses, one that can record on a low scale of abstraction”. The limitations of such a tool are closely related to this notion. It is true that the photographic process offers technical restrictions, but many of the camera’s weaknesses are “fundamentally the weaknesses of those who use it” (Collier & Collier, 1986: 10). It might be difficult for the anthropologist, for instance, to have an impartial view of the subject. Oftentimes, researchers are influenced by their biases and personal projections. This evidently compromises the quality of the study. The fact that “we think and communicate photographically” (Collier & Collier: 1986: 9) is a great advantage. The non-language of photorealism can be understood inter-culturally and cross culturally.

Learning to see with visual accuracy, to see culture in all its complex details is thus a challenge to the fieldworker whose training is literary rather than visual (Collier & Collier, 1986). Modern anthropologists currently use photographs as illustrations rather than as the main content of the research. Many of them feel that the overload of photographic detail constrains a more controlled analysis (Collier & Collier, 1986).

Cultural inventories and material culture

Even though the concept of cultural inventories is most commonly associated with the listing of material goods, as in a store, or the listing of artifacts from an archeological site, it can be extended to other contexts and circumstances. By means of photographs, a cultural inventory can detail “human functions, quality of life, and the nature of psychological well-being” (Collier & Collier, 1986). According to Richardson, with our capacity of making artifacts, we can fix our reality (1982). We therefore use material items, to “recall, reconstitute and communicate our experience” (Richardson, 1982).

To use the example of one’s home, a photographic inventory can record not only a range of artifacts but also their relation to each other as well as other aspects that communicate and elucidate the way people use a room. Since objects reveal a great deal of information about the people who utilize them,

the value of an inventory is connected with the assumption that “the ‘look’ of a home reflects who people are and the way they cope with problems in life” (Collier & Collier, 1986: 45).

Indeed, objects may reflect the identity, the values, and the cultural specificities of an individual or a group of people. However, the inventory deals with more than just material content. The arrangement and use of the space also becomes valuable information that provides insights into the cultural patterns and the well-being of the inhabitants (Collier & Collier, 1986). The photographic inventory remains, therefore, a potentially rich and still untapped use of photography in cultural explorations (Collier & Collier, 1986). It might be employed as a first step towards a comprehension of details of cultural styles, maintenance, and change.

SYMBOLIC MEANINGS IN BUILT ENVIRONMENTS

The analysis of the inventories requires interpretations of symbols incorporated into spaces. Anthropological concern with the built environment is at least as old as the first formalization of theories of cultural evolution during the 19th century (Lawrence & Low, 1990). The concept of the built environment involves products of human building activity: from building types such as dwellings, temples or meetinghouses to open areas such as compounds, plazas, or streets. It may also comprise landmarks or sites.

Symbolic meanings in urban spaces

Urban spaces have been explored as settings for symbolic studies by many researchers. In fact, they are an excellent source of symbols and cultural representations. According to Barthes, cities are privileged semiotic systems (1967). He argues that urban spaces abound with empty signifiers waiting to be filled.

Urban public places are expressions of human endeavours; artefacts of the social world are accommodated, communicated, and interpreted in the confines of this designed environment (Low, 1997). They reflect the population’s diversity in numerous ways. It is in the public spaces that city dwellers manifest their different behaviours, opinion, and beliefs regardless of age, race, gender,

capability, or social status. Everyday users of public areas are often responsible for the meanings that urban elements and spaces assume. By utilizing, adapting or modifying them, these people communicate their level of satisfaction and identification with the city. In this sense, the user becomes “a design’s true producer, who actualizes the design by filling in its gaps or indeterminacies of meaning” (Siu, 2003).

Public spaces also reveal some strong information about how urban planners expect the population to behave. Some are capable of attracting and welcoming people. Even furniture in outdoor areas may embody important and powerful symbolic meanings. Seating and tables in outdoor spaces say, ‘This place is for you’ (Main & Hannah, 2010: 7). Other spaces, on the other hand, repel users either because of the lack of comfort they offer, or the strict rules and surveillance that limit people’s freedom and possibilities of use.

Extraordinary Vienna

Rotenberg’s (1996) analysis on Vienna’s gardens constitutes an exemplary interpretation of symbolic meanings embedded in urban spaces. According to him, the green spaces in this city have become “a medium through which their designers or gardeners express identification with the project, and through it, with the metropolis as a whole” (Rotenberg, 1996: 82). In this sense, the metropolis might be regarded as a city and a cultural movement. The urban landscape, including each park, tree-lined street, palace garden, and domestic lawn, communicates and represents the relationship between the citizen and the metropolitan project. The nine extraordinary landscapes analyzed by Rotenberg epitomize and replicate “the social structure of the city as it evolved historically and spatially” (1996). Whereas the neatly arranged gardens of order suggest that the society should be arranged in a systematic fashion, gardens of liberty advocate free development. Gardens of domesticity replicate the tension between the individual and the society while gardens of refuge reinforce the sense of community and cooperation with reciprocal exchanges of home grown ingredients. Gardens of pleasure present free-flowing planting growth but with a certain geometry on the ground plan derived

of the French curve. Gardens of reform, on the other hand, simplify the pleasure ground aesthetics, with grassy lawns inviting the public to exercise and enjoy the fresh air. Gardens of reaction embody an opposition to the industrial city and display native species of plants whilst gardens of renewal are symbol of health and vigour representing a voluntary recreative activity. Finally, gardens of discovery have meditative qualities and typify a balanced human/garden community.

The metropolitan project is interpreted ideologically through landscape (Rotenberg, 1996). To Rotenberg, green areas in Vienna represent the antagonism between order and liberty as well as public and private according to the political movements that were in power at the time when they were built. The city residents share this system of metaphors because they are introduced to it as children when visiting the referred spaces. In adulthood, they assume their citizenship by identifying themselves with their own strategic predilections, which are normally expressed as aesthetic preferences. Those who have the opportunity to garden can manifest their identity by reproducing the practices of public spaces in their private spaces.

Visualcity

We usually think of the city as a material context, but of course there is more to it than that (Shields, 2003: 3). Shields developed the concept of visualcity to define the actuality of the city which “cannot be captured in one glance” (Shields, 2003: 1). On the contrary, it involves the relationship between the visible and invisible, the tangible and intangible. This implies an interpretation of symbolic meanings rooted in what is seen.

In this context, it is necessary to differentiate the glance from the gaze. The former is a rapid scan that covers a field or context searching for emerging elements of the visual field whilst the latter is “directed at a focus, an icon” (Shields, 2003). The gaze has a depth of field, connecting foreground objects of interest with a broader background. This way, it links the user of the city to its cultural, geographical and historical context.

Representational techniques and exposure emerge as elements capable of supporting a more detailed analysis. They allow scenes to be reproduced or

exposed in diverse media (Shields, 2003).

Photographs, for example, enable the researcher to focus on specific aspects of the scene. City streets and their abundant symbols are “a practical laboratory for photographic analysis of the urban society” (Collier & Collier: 1986: 79). Inventories of photos might be used to catalogue and help the identification and interpretation on the diverse patterns of non-verbal messages spread in these areas.

PUBLIC DESIGN

People are now living in a continuously changing world (Siu, 2009). While cities rapidly develop, public spaces assume more functions, becoming fundamental places for socialization, recreation, and leisure. The designer is faced with the difficult challenge of reconciling needs and differences (Main & Hannah, 2010).

Siu (2009) defends that there is a common lack of in-depth studies regarding the local needs and lifestyles of city dwellers. In order to understand how particular groups of users relate to products, industrial designers should observe cultural issues. By grasping the users’ particular habits and beliefs, these professionals may be capable of developing products that genuinely meet the population’s needs.

Another fact compromises the quality of experience provided by many products displayed in public spaces. According to the case studies conducted by Siu (2009) in Hong Kong, most existing public facilities (including street furniture) in that city are purchased from foreign countries. This phenomenon also happens in other Asian cities and probably in many Western cities as well. Quite a lot of these facilities cannot meet the local cultural and social needs (Siu, 2009). They are not intended to support the particular cultural and social activities performed by specific groups of individuals.

Users’ needs and culture

In order to comprehend the culture of an individual or a particular group of people and how it relates to the quality of the design it is fundamental to understand the spatial and temporal dimensions of culture (Siu, 2009).

Cultures are composed of multiple realities, counterposed against one another like semantic domains and, through this juxtaposition, defining each other (Richardson, 1982). Siu (2005) suggests a model to explain the spatial layers of culture (Figure 1). Each layer represents the structure and the characteristics of a particular culture at a specific period of time. Whereas the inner level is intangible and invisible, the former levels are more concrete and accessible. It is possible, however, to access the inner level by its reflection through the intermediate and outer levels. The inner level affects not only how people (e.g. users of a design object or system) make decisions and act (the intermediate level), but also the design of the physical objects or system (Siu, 2005). The outer level also influences and transforms the intermediate and inner levels. The three levels are therefore closely connected.

Figure 1. Spatial layers of culture inspired by Siu (2005: 546).

Chinese people, for instance, value family reunions, gathering together and sharing. This cultural characteristic has influenced the design and function of physical objects such as round instead of rectangular tables, special utensils for cooking and holding food, and musical instruments, lanterns and lamps to enhance the mood and celebratory atmosphere of gatherings (Siu, 2005). Based on this model, one can conclude that “the quality of the design (the outer level of a culture’s spatial dimension) is inseparable from the behaviour of the users (intermediate level), and from their psychological, social, cultural and also ideological needs and preferences (inner level)” (Siu, 2005).

Users’ responses

Users’ reactions to products and spaces vary. These responses deserve considerable attention from

design researchers. People attempt to reaffirm their cultural identity, often in territorial terms (Low, 1996). Hence, hints of the users’ needs and desires might be concealed in their attitudes towards public spaces. For this reason, industrial and urban designers should attempt to understand “the meaning of urban spaces through the knowledge of the people who live within them” (Rotenberg & McDonogh, 1993). This involves observing the city dwellers’ behaviour including customization of spaces, adaptations and modifications to products and even acts of vandalism.

Siu (2003) defends that participation of the general public “gives a design its meaning”. As an example, he cites footbridges in Hong Kong that were designed only for pedestrian traffic. Instead, they became social gathering places for housewives, resting places for older people, business places for hawkers, playgrounds for skateboarders, a scribble-canvas for youngsters, and homes for beggars (Siu, 2003). Still in Hong Kong, the same author noticed that people used exercise facilities in parks and playgrounds to sun-dry quilts, winter clothes, and salted fish (Siu, 2003). Even with the profusion of laundromats, the elderly traditionally believe that sun-drying clothes is the best way to eliminate germs.

In Montreal, the work of the artist Roadsworth (Figure 2) is another instance of appropriation of urban spaces. He began painting streets in 2001 driven by his need for more bike paths in the city. Creating stencils that challenged what he calls the “car culture”, he intended to point out aspects of the city that should be improved (<http://roadsworth.com>). In 2004, he was arrested for his nocturnal activities and charged with 53 counts of mischief. The public support he received after his arrest, however, contributed in his opinion to minimize his sentence. Since this event, Roadsworth has received numerous commissions for his work. He is still an active artist within the community.

Figure 2. Roadsworth's work (<http://roadsworth.com>)

METHODOLOGY

In order to understand how Ottawa city dwellers relate to public spaces, this study attempted to identify and collect material evidences of users' adaptations to products of public design, and modifications or customizations on urban elements. These indications could enable the researcher to evaluate the previous mentioned user-product relationship and the quality of the design that has been offered to the population. The main goal was to provide designers with valuable insights into the public design activity by making use of visual anthropology research tools. As suggested by Shields (2003), instead of just 'glancing' at the urban spaces, the researcher 'gazed' at users' interventions taking benefit from the advantages that the photographic process offered.

SETTING

Users may develop distinct connections to different places. For this reason, the research explored public spaces in Ottawa that fulfilled different functions. Residential, commercial, and recreative spaces were investigated. The research also looked at and analyzed areas that attracted different amounts of people as well as places under extreme surveillance and those frequently unobserved by the public. Finally, both monumental and gathering spaces were selected. The study embraced the Byward Market area, the Parliament Hill, the surroundings of Sparks and Bank streets, and the Ottawa River region in downtown Ottawa.

MEASUREMENT INSTRUMENTS

The unstructured observation enabled the researcher to find the different users' responses to the urban elements and spaces. Photographs were used to document the several instances of city dwellers' influences in the public spaces. While allowing the researcher to focus on details, the pictures also facilitated the identification of patterns and clusters in the users' actions.

DATA COLLECTION

Data was collected during the months of October and November 2010 in Ottawa's downtown area. The researcher covered the previously mentioned areas by walking, looking for the differences in the ways city dwellers demonstrated their relationship to public spaces. In this sense, instances of adaptations to products functions, modifications to the elements' appearance, and even people's artistic manifestation became data for analysis.

DATA ANALYSIS

The interpretation of data included the transposition of visual components into verbal information. No analysis of photographs can ignore this crucial translation process; although it may be that some research insight and knowledge cannot be fully transformed to verbal forms (Collier & Collier, 1986). First, photographs were submitted to a period of free and unstructured examination. Then, they were compared and grouped in clusters, which were labelled according to the form of intervention. They were also organized in compliance with the function of the place where they were taken. The intention was to find patterns of behaviour in the users' actions. The patterns were aimed to provide designers with insight that could assist them in the development of public designs.

RESULTS

The investigation resulted in a large number of photos, which represented the varied ways people react to public spaces and intervene in urban elements. In general, places that aggregated greater quantities of people, presented a large number of interventions. Many instances of adaptations made by users were spotted in the Byward Market area,

and the Bank Street surroundings (Figure 3). In spaces with smaller concentrations of users, on the other hand, few or no examples of modifications were encountered. The surroundings of Sparks Street and the Parliament generally presented a small number of customized elements as well.

Figure 3. Instances of adaptations made by users in the Byward Market area and the Bank Street surroundings

Another factor that strongly influenced the users' actions was the level of surveillance to which the area is submitted. In the Parliament area, there was practically no evidence of active participation of people in the urban environment. A sign prohibiting the use of skateboards constitutes an attestation of the limited freedom city dwellers experience in such areas. In contrast, people easily appropriated areas that are not carefully watched. Abandoned places and temporary structures often displayed numerous interventions (Figure 4).

Figure 4. Abandoned places and temporary structures

FUNCTIONAL NEEDS

Some interventions clearly manifested the users' functional needs which were not fulfilled by the urban space. Additional chairs and bicycles leaning on fences fall into this category of adaptation (Figure 5). They tend to reveal a lack of urban equipment to support the activities that users perform in the space.

Figure 5. Manifestations of users' functional needs

4.2 CULTURAL, SOCIAL, PSYCHOLOGICAL AND IDEOLOGICAL NEEDS

Other manifestations could not be so simply interpreted. They revealed some of the users' more abstract needs. The study identified, for instance, an unforeseen role that public design products might assume. City dwellers habitually use urban elements to convey messages. Frequently, they affix posters and artworks on street lights and other urban elements despite the fees that punish acts of vandalism. In addition, some individuals use graffiti, varied calligraphies, and other painting techniques to express ideas in public spaces also violating the law. The investigation recognized three main possible purposes that the messages attached to urban equipment might serve: commercial, ideological, and personal/artistic (Figure 6). The last two categories were particularly important to this investigation since they could offer unique potential to reveal symbolic and cultural meanings. With the purpose of facilitating an examination of their content, such interventions were classified in three categories: verbal, pictorial, and sculptural messages.

Figure 6. People's ideological and personal/artistic expressions

TEXTUAL MESSAGES

In some cases, the users made use of common language and words to express ideas such as 'imagine'. These ideas were probably intended to be read and understood by the population. Expressions of hope or protest aimed to target on city dwellers were also a common example of this kind of message. The expression 'socialism' placed below the images of jokers (Figure 6) can be assumed to represent some sort of ideological disapproval or ironic symbolism towards economic and political systems.

On other occasions, even if the population can visually read the information, the in-depth meaning remains unknown. The expression 'dubium' (Figure 6), for instance, probably does represent a clear message to most people. It might function as the author's cognomen as well as a legend for the drawing that is above it. The study also identified words that seemed to be proper names, identifying the people who signed it. The word 'Ostela' (Figure 7), for example, may constitute an example of personal signature. Such manifestations appear to be common examples of attempts to appropriate the spaces.

Finally, an occasional system of symbols was used. Those who were not familiar with the code could not read the message. Graffiti interventions fall into this category. These interventions are largely utilized by gangs who intend to demarcate territories or communicate with other street groups.

PICTORIAL MESSAGES

Alongside with the use of textual messages, city dwellers also express themselves by using drawings and pictorial images with varied contents. The examples here collected throughout the investigation display representations of an animal and a person or character (Figure 7). In other instances, the message is more complex as in the case of a picture where the shadow of a man shoots himself (Figure 6). This image allows multiple interpretations. Similar to a critical piece of art, it invites the viewer to elaborate his/her own understanding.

Regardless of their shape, the material that functioned as a support for the interventions revealed some similarities. In most cases, for both

textual and pictorial messages, people made use of clear surfaces that did not present details or textures. Postal boxes were recurrently utilized as canvases for people's expressions. Interestingly, in the case of the figures analyzed in this paper, the majority of the elements which received the users' imprint did not incorporate colourful features either. Indeed, gray coloured backgrounds seemed to be predominant in the observed urban spaces.

Figure 7. Pictorial messages

SCULPTURAL MESSAGES

In a more contemplative area of the city, an unconventional sort of users' contribution to public areas was pinpointed. At the Ottawa River margins, natural elements served as material for interventions. Both the artist John Felice Ceprano (Figure 8) and anonymous city dwellers (Figure 9) used the river stones in order to make statements in urban spaces. The installations built by the artist were ephemeral sculptures, which were supposed to be destroyed by the nature in the winter. The pieces built by unidentified people evoke the inuksuk¹. In the summer, many similar shapes can be spotted in the same area.

In both cases, there seemed to be a need for expressing elements of the Canadian culture, which is very connected to nature and climate. In the particular case of the inuksuk replication, the cultural inheritance appeared in a stronger and more literal fashion, possibly demonstrating the authors' pride for Inuit traditions.

¹Inuksuit were guides to traveling Inuit, for directions, and were usually built on rising ground, so that they showed above blowing snow. Rows of inuksuit were built to look like rows of human beaters, to frighten caribou into a certain path where the hunters are waiting for them with bows and arrows, or across water where the hunters were waiting in kayaks with spears. But they were not necessarily always functional. Many times, Inuit while stopping for tea or some other reason on the trail, may gather stones and pile up an inuksuk, just as "Something to do," as a record that "I was here" just as people in the south sometimes scrawl "Kilroy was here." In one trip along the shore of the Hudson Bay, we waited while a pair of mating dogs in our team became unstuck so we built an inuksuk near the shore to pass time (Grabum, 2004: 70).

Figure 8. John Felice Ceprano's sculptures

Figure 9. Anonymous city dwellers' installations

DISCUSSION

As stated by Ruby (2000), “a passive camera used to create pure observational-style film does not reveal culture”. Likewise, the cultural inventory by itself does not unveil the singular attributes of the population in focus. The researcher must interpret and, by some means, generalize his comprehension about singular behaviours to an entire cultural group. The examination of the Parliament area disclosed spaces that correspond to the gardens of order observed by Rotenberg in Vienna (1996). Similarly to these gardens, the Parliament’s surroundings praise the government and the role of the capital city. The area is linearly and geometrically organized, representing through a metaphor how city dwellers should behave in it. Comparably to the metropolitans in Vienna, who know that “urban places are filled with the ideological messages of social movements that permeated city life at the time their gardens were built” (Rotenberg, 1996), Ottawa city dwellers understand and share the symbolic meanings expressed by the place. As previously mentioned, even though the meanings are imposed, residents are familiar with them because they are in contact with them since their childhood (Rotenberg, 1996). In other cases, the identification with urban spaces is not as direct. It seems that city users are eager to manifest their own ideas, beliefs, and emotions especially in areas which do not retain a strong

symbolic nature. Different from Viennese city dwellers, who are able to express their ideological opinions “as aesthetic attitudes” (Rotenberg, 1996) by gardening and reproducing the spatial practices of the public spaces in private gardens, Ottawa citizens do not have many opportunities to convey their own messages. Consequently, they use urban elements, frequently the most unembellished and non-ornamented ones, as blank canvases to imprint their mark.

The anthropological perspective on culture may assume an important role in the interpretation of the city dwellers’ behaviour. The fact that the public needs to adapt and modify urban spaces and equipment might be regarded as evidence that they may be improved to completely fulfil people’s needs. Observations on public spaces can result in important insights into public design activity.

It became evident, for example, that the population’s non-functional needs are very connected to the desire for expressing their ideas, appropriating spaces, and developing emotional identification with them. Industrial designers might acknowledge these desires as a chance to innovate. Empathizing with the users and creating opportunities for them to participate in the development of urban elements should be some of the designers’ fundamental concerns. For instance, in designing a community park, or public furniture, the design with the highest degree of user fitness is usually the one that allows and encourages residents to voice their preferences, and to make modifications to fit their community and individual needs (Siu, 2003).

In the literature, it is possible to find successful instances of public involvement in public spaces. King, Ferrari, Conley and Latimer (1989) relate the Wessburn Park, Burnaby, British Columbia example. In 1977, the population, including children, were invited to paint murals over the entire exterior of a community centre. According to these authors, the action curtailed vandalism. Although there has been some controversy regarding their claims, it makes sense to affirm that since people started to use the area intensely and take care for it vigilantly, the incidences of acts of vandalism were reduced. In this case, it is possible to infer that the public developed a connection with the space. By creating the murals’

pictorial content, they could also express their ideas, desires, and cultural background.

In similar fashion, a more recent initiative in Rio de Janeiro, Brazil included the community in decisions related to their neighbourhood. The purpose of the *Favela Painting* project, founded by the Dutch artists Haas and Hahn, is to involve the local youth in the development of art interventions in the Brazilian shantytowns (www.favelapainting.com). Even though the public does not completely create the artworks that will be applied to the murals, they are consulted and are given the right to choose between some alternatives. An example of an artwork chosen by the community is the boy with a kite illustration (Figure 10). In this case, the favela dwellers were given many options but decided to have an image that represents an activity that is common in their lives stamped on their walls: flying kites. Again, the population was given an opportunity to develop an emotional attachment to the space. The intervention expresses elements of the local culture which are recognized and understood by the public.

Figure 10. The boy with a kite illustration (www.favelapainting.com)

Most examples of public participation, however, present superficial community involvement. While it is important that the public be able to define the appearance of their neighbourhood and express their opinions and cultural specificities, it might also be beneficial to the population to have the opportunity to participate in a deeper way, manifesting their needs and desires and influencing more decisions than merely the painting of the urban elements. Further research might investigate the possibility of transforming vandalism into public participation. It is possible that when the population is heard and

seriously considered by the planners, rebellious actions may become less frequent. In this case, instead of using their energy to modify public property by violating the law, people could be invited to negotiate with decision-makers alternatives to fulfil their needs.

CONCLUSION

Urban users' requirements have changed. This becomes particularly evident in public spaces where city dwellers wish to have their social, cultural, psychological and ideological needs met. When urban elements fail to fulfil the public's desires, people attempt to adapt to adequately support the activities they want to perform. In order to appropriate space, they utilize urban elements for purposes that differ from the planned uses. Furthermore, they add personal, artistic or ideological messages to objects. These interventions often occur in an illicit way and interfere with the city's facade.

Only through in-depth and continuous studies on cultures and daily-life practices of the urban users can we achieve designs with a high degree of user fitness (Siu, 2005). For this reason, the association between visual anthropology and public design might produce exceptionally positive outcomes. Whilst designers possess exceptional visual skills and can easily interpret the content of pictures, anthropologists are capable of identifying the implicit meanings of people's behaviours and manifestations. Anthropologists have a better knowledge breadth and much deeper understanding of the specificities of cultures and can distinguish more details in the city dwellers' experience in spaces.

Both disciplines can work together in order to create solutions to satisfy the needs of these increasingly vital public areas. Innovative public design products may result from a better comprehension of user demands. Moreover, the shift of focus from physical needs to cultural knowledge may contribute to the encouragement of negotiations between users, designers, and decision makers. The involvement of every stakeholder in city issues, including the design discussion, might culminate in public spaces that will be celebrated and embraced by the whole population.

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